

Status of the NJOY Modernization

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ABSTRACT

The modernized version of the NJOY Nuclear Data Processing System is being built from a series of components that enable the traditional work required of the production version of NJOY while also providing a much more interactive user experience through a modern interface. Over the past year, significant changes were made to the nuclear data interface that forms the backbone of modern NJOY. These changes include new integration methods for integration of tabulated data to calculate mean values, development of a new covariance data structure, transformation of probability distributions into cumulative distributions and the addition of support for GNDS formatted nuclear data files. All this has culminated in the creation of the new eprdata25 photoatomic and electroatomic data library for MCNP which was produced using only modern NJOY components. The validation work for this new data library has not shown any significant issues with the processing and produces results similar to the previous eprdata14 library.

Keywords: NJOY, nuclear data, photoatomic, electroatomic

1. INTRODUCTION

The NJOY Nuclear Data Processing System [1] developed at Los Alamos National Laboratory is used to manipulate evaluated nuclear data into forms such as the ACE (A Compact ENDF) and NDI (Nuclear Data Interface, a multigroup format) formats that can be consumed by application codes such as MCNP [2] and PARTISN [3] respectively. It performs physics operations such as linearizing cross-section data, computing coefficients needed for nuclear heating calculations, and computing multigroup constants for deterministic transport. It also translates data into formats required by the application codes.

This code was first developed in the 1970s and a recapitalization effort was needed to retain knowledge of the operations NJOY performs, to ensure it remains operational and efficient on modern computers, and to continue to adapt to evolving nuclear data evaluations [4]. The emergence of the GNDS (Generalized Nuclear Database Structure) [5] format as an alternative to ENDF [6] would also require an extensive overhaul of NJOY's code base, which gives sufficient motivation to perform this effort now.

The legacy NJOY code is built around monolithic processing modules, each performing a specific task. For example, the RECONR module reconstructs resonances and linearizes cross-sections, BROADR performs Doppler broadening on those cross-sections, and ACER formats the data into an ACE file. Temporary ENDF files are used to transfer information in between these various modules. This monolithic structure of NJOY is most useful when processing full evaluations into application libraries, but it is highly inefficient for a wide range of other applications. Users now prefer more flexibility, perhaps asking simple questions, e.g., what is the cross-section value at a specific energy, or are interested in some of the intermediate results produced during the NJOY processing that are not available in the output, e.g., retrieving the elements of the R-matrix during resonance reconstruction.

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Figure 1. The design of a modernized NJOY: format components for evaluated data and application libraries feed into the *dryad* interface which can be accessed by processing components.

The modernized version of NJOY is being built from a series of components that enable routine work while also providing a much more interactive user experience through a modern interface. Components can be stitched together to create end-to-end processing modules desired by many users without sacrificing the desired flexibility. Furthermore, this component-based approach allows users to take advantage of newly developed components prior to the completion of the modern NJOY project.

Modern NJOY is being developed in C++, which was determined to be the language of choice given computational efficiency requirements and the compatibility with modern software engineering practices. However, the desire to have a flexible, powerful and simple user interface also necessitates incorporating Python bindings, as users almost universally prefer scripting languages over compiled languages for their applications. Python bindings also allow prototype development in the comparatively easy to use Python language rather than immediately optimizing for performance in C++.

In what follows, we will provide an update on the modernization work performed over the last year. We will detail updates to the nuclear data interface for secondary particle distributions, covariance data and support for the GNDS format (section 2) before going into details on the processing of the eprdata25 ACE files for photoatomic and electroatomic data from the ENDF/B-VIII.1 nuclear data libraries.

2. A Format Agnostic Nuclear Data Interface

Legacy NJOY reads data from ENDF files, and from disk, whenever it needs data such as cross-section values, resonance parameters, etc. It also uses temporary ENDF files, also stored on disk, to transfer information between different modules. Modern NJOY will also need a way to transfer information from one module to another, but for efficiency reasons we should now prefer in-memory data instead of storing temporary data on disk.

With the advent of the GNDS format it is also important for these in-memory data structures to be independent of format specific details. The reaction data is laid out differently between the ENDF and GNDS formats, even though they contain the same data. The ENDF format structures the data by type, meaning that a user can find all cross-section data for every reaction in MF3 while the angular and energy distribution data for every reaction can be found in either MF4 and MF5, or in MF6. For GNDS on the other hand, all data for a single reaction is stored within the same hierarchical reaction node.

Within NJOY, the *dryad* component [7] is going to provide this interface and will therefore become the backbone of a modernized NJOY as illustrated in Figure 1. The principal object in *dryad* (the *ProjectileTarget*) represents all the data available for projectile on target data, whether the

interaction is nuclear or atomic. Almost all nuclear data would fit in here, an exception being the decay data and thermal scattering data. It will also contain all possible information ranging from resonance parameters to reaction data (including cross-sections, reaction products, multiplicities and distributions) and covariance data. Specialized processed data such as heating numbers, damage cross-sections and unresolved resonance probability tables can be tacked on as well during the processing workflow. For people familiar with the GNDS structure, all this will look and feel familiar as the higher-level hierarchy of GNDS is also laid out like this.

2.1. Support for the GNDS evaluated nuclear data format

As was mentioned in the introduction, one of the incentives for the modernization of NJOY has been the creation of the GNDS format for evaluated nuclear data. Over the past year, we have added support for reading GNDS files, or at least for the same data we already read from ENDF files. The focus here has been the atomic relaxation data and the photoatomic and electroatomic evaluated data because it was a requirement to produce the eprdata25 ACE files (see section 3 for more information on this).

The atomic relaxation data gives all data necessary to calculate the spectrum of photons (X-rays) and Auger electrons following the ionization of an atom in an atomic interaction. This data gives binding energies for all electron subshells, their populations (when in the ground state) and the probabilities for all possible transitions between electron subshells. The ENDF format also lists the energy of the outgoing electron or photon, but the GNDS format omits this value since it can be calculated from the electron subshell binding energies.

The photoatomic and electroatomic data consists of cross-section data for all possible atomic interactions, secondary angular and/or energy distributions for the secondary particles and energy loss data. Since most of these secondary particle distributions are based on tabulated distributions, only those representations are currently implemented for use in *dryad*.

For the other incident particle data (i.e. incident neutron, incident charged particle and photonuclear data), all cross-section data for each reaction is populated as well as all reaction products and their multiplicity. And as mentioned in the previous section, we also read all cross-section covariance data from ENDF and GNDS files. The secondary particle distribution data for these incident particle types are, at the time of writing, still limited to the incident neutron's elastic scattering distributions but that will change soon.

The GNDS format provides the ability to specify physical data in a wide variety of units, contrary to the ENDF format that uses a single reference unit for each type of physical data (e.g. energies in eV, masses in neutron mass units, cross-sections in barn, etc.). To avoid storing unit information and unnecessary conversion during processing, *dryad* currently converts all GNDS data to the reference units used internally. In the future, we may replace this with compile-time units and unit conversion.

To ensure that all floating-point data are read and interpreted in the same way between an ENDF and GNDS file, we are using the `fast_float` floating point parser [8] across all NJOY libraries that parse floating point strings. We could have used C++ standard capabilities for floating point parsing (as provided by the `std::from_chars` standard function added in the C++-17 standard). However, since we have found that some standard library implementations do not provide a full implementation of the `std::from_chars` function, we have had to change to using the `fast_float` parser. As an added benefit, the `fast_float` parser also provides an extension to allow for parsing Fortran formatted floating point strings (as one would encounter in the ENDF format). This switch has improved parsing efficiency by about 20% across the board.

2.2. New features for secondary particle distribution data

Many processing operations in NJOY require some sort of integration of data. Basic examples would be the calculation of mean values from distribution data (for instance to calculate the average secondary particle energy in the HEATR module) or the calculation of a cumulative distribution from another distribution (which is required when processing data into ACE files for MCNP). The math library for modern NJOY (referred to as *scion*) already has quite a few capabilities for integration, including numerical integration such as Gauss-Legendre or Gauss-Lobatto. While such numerical integration

techniques are quite effective for integrating arbitrary functions, tabulated data (and functions with analytical forms) can probably be integrated more efficiently using analytical integration. Instead of evaluating a function multiple times for each interval in numerical integration, we can simply use the antiderivative or primitive over the interval if these can be easily calculated. It would even be possible to do this for other higher-level raw or central moments of tabulated data if the need for it arises.

Analytical integration for tabulated data to integrate and calculate mean values has been added to the `scion` library [7], for all possible interpolation types. This is in turn used in `dryad` to allow for the calculation of the integral and mean value of any tabulated distribution (without having to linearize the distribution), just like what was already available for Legendre based distributions. Now that both tabulated and Legendre distributions can be integrated, `dryad` can normalize distribution data while reading an evaluated nuclear data file or on demand by the user for individual distributions. The new integration capabilities are also used to automatically calculate the cumulative distribution of any tabulated distribution (regardless of interpolation type) without user intervention. This capability was required for the production of the `eprdata25` ACE files (see section 3 for more information on this).

These new capabilities are illustrated in Figure 2 which gives the elastic scattering angular distributions and their associated cumulative distributions for Pu239 from ENDF/B-VIII.1.

Figure 2. Pu239 elastic scattering pdf (left) and cdf (right) data from ENDF/B-VIII.1, as provided by `dryad`. The evaluated data is given as Legendre moments so the distribution data was linearized for these graphs.

2.3. The new covariance data structure

Another new feature that has been added to the `dryad` interface is a new covariance data structure. When characterizing covariance data, we often associate a number of dimensions to the rows and columns of the full matrix. This is illustrated in Figure 3 which gives a schematic layout of a covariance matrix associated with reaction product multiplicities or fission product yields. The matrix in the middle represents the full matrix, composed of multiple sub-matrices. Each row and column of the full matrix is associated with an energy group structure while the rows and column of the sub-matrices are associated with reaction products. Every sub-matrix is thus associated with both a row energy group and a column energy group. When both are the same, the sub-matrix is on-diagonal and is also a covariance matrix for all reaction products in the given incident energy group – as can be seen on the left in Figure 3. The other sub-matrices are off-diagonal and represent cross terms between energy groups, as can be seen on the right in Figure 3. Each additional dimension adds another level for these sub-matrices. If we add reactions as a third dimension, we can now also consider cross terms between reactions and so on. This basically means that to allow for additional cross terms of a specific kind, we only need to add another dimension on top.

Figure 3. Schematic overview of a full covariance matrix for reaction product multiplicity covariance data.

For *dryad*, we have now developed a covariance data structure using a matrix and associated row and column keys, in which the keys are tuples of values for the various dimensions of the matrix. In the example of Figure 3, the entire matrix would have 6 keys (3 values for the energy group dimension and 2 values for the reaction product dimension) and each of the individual submatrices would have 2 keys (1 value for the energy group dimension and 2 values for the reaction product dimension). As a result, this data structure can be used to store both the entire matrix (including any cross terms) and individual sub-matrices, regardless of how many dimensions are applied to the matrix. For processed covariance data, we can thus use a single matrix laid out like this while we can use multiple individual matrices for the raw evaluated data, all with the same interface.

This covariance matrix data structure can be initialized using covariance values or using standard deviations and correlation values (from which covariance values are computed upon construction). Standard deviations, correlations and eigenvalues can be calculated and stored on demand by the user. This interface provides us with all tools to perform covariance data testing, both on processed and evaluated covariance data. An additional feature that was added recently is the ability to extract sub-matrices based on values of the keys, for example to extract the covariance data for all energy groups and a single reaction product in the example of Figure 3.

dryad can currently store cross-section covariance data (using reactions and energy groups as dimensions) and reaction product multiplicity covariance data (using reactions, energy groups and reaction products as dimensions). The reaction identifiers used in *dryad* also specify the incident particle, the target, and outgoing particles. Cross terms with different targets and even incident particle types are therefore supported by default. We can currently read the evaluated covariance data from an ENDF or GND file, and from processed GENDF files from the ERRORR module from NJOY.

3. Processing Photoatomic and Electroatomic data

The Electron-Photon-Relaxation data (EPRDATA) format is a relatively new continuous-energy atomic data file type which has been available for users of MCNP since 2013 with the release of the *eprdata12* ACE library [9]. An EPRDATA library combines the traditional photoatomic data library used for Monte Carlo photon transport with atomic relaxation data and electron cross-section data which can be used for single-event electron transport. An upgraded library, *eprdata14*, was released in 2015 [10] featuring data refinement as well as expansion of the format description to provide new transport-corrected and total elastic cross-sections. Most recently, the latest EPR data [11] has been incorporated into the ENDF/B-VIII.0 and VIII.1 releases, but these updates have not yet been processed into the EPRDATA format for use by MCNP.

Contrary to other ACE types, EPRDATA style files were not produced using NJOY. Because of this, and the fact that no resonance reconstruction or Doppler broadening is required in processing EPR data, the production of the *eprdata25* library based on ENDF/B-VIII.1 was selected as the first application of modern NJOY. The development of this capability required adding the necessary support for the

evaluated data (as detailed in section 2.1), integration of probability distributions to produce cumulative distributions (as detailed in section 2.2) and the calculation of a transport corrected elastic cross-section (which also uses some of the integration updates mentioned in section 2.2). Existing capabilities have been extended as well, such as the unionization of the energy grids of the cross-sections which is a requirement for any ACE file.

The eprdata25 library is based on the same evaluated data sources as the preceding eprdata14 library and does not feature an extension of the EPRDATA format. Therefore, improvements in the new library originate from corrections and fixes to the evaluated data. The most significant improvement of eprdata25 over its predecessors is the inclusion of updated subshell energies for all interaction types. Revisions to the subshell energies lead to more accurate photoelectric and electro-ionization cross-sections, corrections to the Doppler broadening model for photon incoherent scattering energy distributions, and improved transition energies for line radiation and Auger electron emission. Other smaller changes are included in eprdata25. The most recent evaluated data has removed photo-excitation from the photon scattering data as it was considered unimportant for applications and difficult to evaluate accurately, and this change has propagated to eprdata25.

Figure 5. Stopping power comparison between the eprdata14 and eprdata25 data for Be (left) and Cu (right).

Figure 6. Comparison of electron backscattering from Cu between the eprdata14 and eprdata25 data, including results from condensed history calculations.

To validate this new eprdata25 library, several test cases from the MCNP V&V suite for electron transport have been selected and are related to the calculation of electron stopping powers and electron backscattering [12].

For the electron stopping power calculations, the MCNP code is used to simulate single-event transport with a specified EPRDATA library, after which electron stopping powers and ranges are calculated from distances between energy-loss events along each source electron track. Figure 5 gives an example comparing the electron stopping powers calculated with eprdata25 versus eprdata14. In general, calculations with eprdata25 show improved agreement with semi-empirical stopping power measurements at electron energies at or above 300 eV, with the root-mean-square error reduced by 10% to 25% depending on the element. This improved agreement is due to the corrected subshell energies in the ENDF/B-VIII.1 data. For electron energies below 300 eV, there is no clear improvement or worsening of the agreement compared to the eprdata14 library, which is expected since the cross-section values at these low energies are known to be unreliable. Generally, eprdata25 gives slightly higher stopping powers at these low energies since the subshell energies (and thus electron energy loss) were generally revised upwards.

Figure 6 gives an example comparing electron backscattering yields calculated with eprdata25 to those calculated with eprdata14. In general, both eprdata25 and eprdata14 offer good agreement with the experimental measurements for energies above 1 keV. Due to the spread in experimental data, it is not clear which library gives more accurate predictions, but since eprdata25 is a relatively minor revision the close agreement between the two libraries is unsurprising. For electron energies below 1 keV, both EPRDATA libraries suffer from a discontinuity in the cross-section data which is a known limitation. The eprdata25 backscattering yields are typically slightly lower than those calculated with eprdata14, as visible in Figure 6, which is attributable to increased energy loss of the incident electrons due to the general across-the-board increase in subshell binding energies already mentioned above.

Figure 6 also shows results for backscattering yields computed using the condensed history method. The single-event transport with an EPRDATA library clearly gives better accuracy than condensed history transport for scattering problems, particularly for incident electron energies below 100 keV. This is as expected, since the condensed history method incorporates only small-angle multiple scattering without the critical large-angle scattering events.

In general, the validation work presented here has not shown any significant issues with the processing of the new eprdata25 library. It is also interesting to note that the use of ENDF formatted or GNDS formatted data when processing the eprdata25 library led to the exact same ACE files, without even any round-off difference.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have given an overview of the current state of the NJOY modernization effort. The modernized version of NJOY is being built from a series of components that enable the work required of NJOY while also providing a much more interactive user experience through a modern interface. This new version of NJOY is being developed in C++ and Python bindings above this C++ interface are provided as well.

Over the past year, we have added support for reading GNDS files, or at least for the same data we already read from ENDF files. The focus here has been the atomic relaxation data and the photoatomic and electroatomic evaluated data from which we can now read all data. For the other incident particle data (i.e. incident neutron, incident charged particle and photonuclear data), all cross-section data for each reaction is populated as well as all reaction products and their multiplicity. Cross-section covariance data is also included. The secondary particle distribution data for these incident particle types are, at the time of writing, still limited to the incident neutron's elastic scattering distributions but that will change soon.

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distribution data can now be normalized while reading an evaluated nuclear data file or on demand by the user for individual distributions. These new integration capabilities are also used to automatically calculate the cumulative distribution of any tabulated distribution.

Another new feature that has been added to the `dryad` interface is a new covariance data structure. This covariance matrix data structure can be initialized using covariance values or using standard deviations and correlation values. It can be used to store both an entire matrix (including any cross terms) and individual submatrices. For processed covariance data, we can thus use a single matrix laid out like this while we can use multiple individual matrices for the raw evaluated data, all with the same interface.

All this has culminated in the creation of the new `eprdata25` photoatomic and electroatomic data library for MCNP which was produced using only modern NJOY components. The validation work presented for this new data library has not shown any significant issues with the processing and produces results similar to the previous `eprdata14` library.

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